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SYNERGIES OF BIOSYSMO PROJECT WITH THE MISSION SOIL INITIATIVE

The Mission Soil initiative is a comprehensive effort dedicated to the protection, restoration, and sustainable management of soils in both urban and rural settings. The primary objectives of Mission Soil encompass increasing awareness and securing the enduring health and productivity of soils across diverse landscapes. Furthermore, the mission strives to disseminate knowledge to stakeholders and the public, emphasising sustainable practices in spatial planning, soil conservation, and agriculture. The overarching goal is to minimise the reliance on chemical inputs for a more sustainable and resilient approach.

The eight particular goals of the EU Missions soil deal for Europe are as follows:

- Improve soil structure to improve soil habitat quality for soil biota and crops;
- Reduce the EU's global footprint on soils;
- Increase soil literacy in society,
- Reduce land degradation related to desertification;
- Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks;
- Increase reuse of urban soils;
- Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration;
- And prevent erosion.

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Furthermore, soils are essential to the ecosystem because they:

- produce safe and nutrient-rich food, wood, fibers, etc.;
- cycling nutrients;
- store and cycling carbon;
- support biodiversity;
- purify and regulate water cycles;
- prevent floods and droughts;
- and support human activities, landscapes, and cultural heritage.

ADDITIONALLY, BIOSYSMO LINKS ITS SIGNIFICANCE TO THE FOLLOWING FACTORS:

1. Pollutant Degradation: The project intends to address the presence of pollutants in the environment and their influence on soil health. It focuses on establishing biosystems for the effective degradation and sequestration of pollutant mixtures. This is directly connected to the problem of soil pollution.
2. Biodiversity and Microorganisms: This area of study focuses on the identification and use of microorganisms, such as fungus and bacteria, for the degradation of pollutants. It is pertinent to the significance of soil biodiversity and the critical role that microorganisms play in preserving soil health.
3. Nutrient Cycling and Carbon Storage: BIOSYSMO indirectly aids in the restoration of these essential soil activities by promoting pollutant degradation.
4. Soil Health and Management: The project creates techniques for removing pollutants from the soil and enhancing its quality, which promotes both sustainable soil management and health.

The primary concerns of BIOSYSMO are pollution, healthy soil, and sustainable soil management; these issues are in accordance with the objectives and concerns expressed in the EU Missions soil deal of Europe.

BIOSYSMO at the EU Mission Soil Week

The BIOSYSMO project, represented by our partners UBU and UBFC, also participated in the European Mission Soil Week held in Madrid, Spain from November 21 to 23, 2023. This significant event aimed to highlight the critical aspects of soil protection, restoration, and monitoring, fostering discussions on sustainable solutions for land management. During the event our representatives had the opportunity to meet up with some of our cluster projects including [PrepSoil](#), [InBestSoil](#), [Loess](#), [ISLANDR](#), [Solo](#), [Edaphos](#), and [MIBIREM](#).